

“THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SPEAKING SKILL”

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Abstract

The main purpose of this article is to learn the development of speaking, principles of teaching and also the ability to speak effectively. The information in the article will be used for improving our speaking skill

Abstrakt

Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi-nutqni rivojlantirish, o'qitish tamoyillari va shuningdek samarali gapirish qobiliyatini o'rganishdir. Maqoladagi ma'lumotlar nutq mahoratimizni oshirish uchun ishlatiladi.

Keywords: speaking, verbal and non-verbal communication, communication approach, communication competence

Kalit so'zlar: nutq, og'zaki va og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqot, kommunikatsiya yondashuvi hamda kommunikatsiya vakolati

Speaking is one of the four macro skills necessary for effective communication in any language, particularly when speakers are not using their mother tongue. As English is universally used as a means of communication, especially in the internet world, English speaking skills should be developed along with the other skills so that these integrated skills will enhance communication achievement both with native speakers of English and other members of the international community. Because of the significant role of speaking in action, Bailey detailed how to enhance the development of speaking by means of syllabus design, principles of teaching, types of tasks and materials, and speaking assessment.

Being able to speak actively is an important communication skill. This is easily ignored, since attracting attention to what people are saying, instead of listening to what another person is saying in order to grow confidence in presentation skills. An important skill to know when pausing to talk to another person. It is respected and respected to view the other person's perspective. Active speaking skills will help you and your colleagues more open and useful exchanges, where each participant's views can be expressed and heard. This will be a more positive work environment. The importance of speaking skills in communication has no limit. To become a better spinner, four language skills such as listening, talking, reading, and writing skills, but with the ability to speak efficiently, speak to the speaker with a variety of advantages. The ability to express ideas, opinions, and feelings, as well as sound words together, offers the speakers these benefits. The pleasure of sharing ideas with others is immense. When we talk to others, our own spontaneous intelligence is understood, as Robert Frost once said: "I'm not the author of the book of the past, I'm talking about understanding, learning to learn." Undoubtedly, transparency in speech reflects clear thinking. An effective speaker can capture the audience's attention and keep the message up until the end. Speaking skills are important for career success, but of course, your professional desire is not limited. Improving speaking skills in English will enhance your career and personal life. Many people tend to tend too much effort into specific skills and not enough into others. Interestingly enough, most people want to be really good to say skills. They practice at least. In the next few posts, we will discuss ways to practice your speaking skills in language learning.

Bruce Lee quote says: "Knowing is not enough, we have to apply. Bill is not enough, we must do it". Sure, it can all be Jane and Philosophical Words, but it is very true! However, it is not nearly as convenient for other reasons as people do not practice speaking more efficiently. Good to learn at home on your computer, but you need people to practice talking. As a human, our mother tongue is a conversation that is something we have to do with second nature. But for computers, conversations are very complex and it's just a few things they cannot fix. A computer can solve complex complexes, remember the data, play better chess than the world champions, but they

cannot make an interesting conversation with you. Of course, you can ask a virtual junkie on your phone to say a joke, but let's face it, they are often quite lazy. To practice your speaking skills, you have to talk to real people (I'm scary). Fortunately, computers can not actually connect to your conversations, but they can certainly help you find these great conversations. Your new language might be nice to have a basic foundation before you go outside the world, but do not try to wait too long! We believe that it is good to try to talk as soon as you start learning, even when it goes to foreign destinations, it's easy to say "hello" and "thank you"

Verbal communication

When we communicate orally, it incorporates not only speaking but also non verbal communication skills like listening, eye contact, and body language. Mispronunciations, insufficient language skills, or struggling with diction can greatly affect a person's ability to get their message across by attaining speaking skills in English. Also, delivering too much information How we communicate is dependent on the context of the situation too. A different approach is needed for different situations. The importance of speaking skills in communication has no limit with skills in public speaking.

Non-verbal communication

Body language needs to be in line with the verbal content. When used effectively, facial expressions, gestures, and posture can greatly improve the listener's report. It can also add interest to have skills in speaking. Eye contact between speaker and listeners is important too If a speaker actively seeks out eye contact when talking, he or she is judged to be more believable, confident, and competent. However, too much eye contact can make the person feel uncomfortable, or think the speaker rude, hostile, and condescending; and too little eye contact can make the listener think that the speaker is uneasy, unsure, or insincere. How much eye contact is considered appropriate, the setting, cultural expectations, gender, and personality types and confidence to speak in public.

The communicative approach was developed in the early 1970's by the studies of the European Council and the contributions of many linguists, such as an American

psychiatrist and psychoanalyst Robert Langs MD, known as an important psychoanalytic revolutionist and revisionist trained in a classical Freudian psychoanalytic institute in New York City, to the communicative approach and language teaching, and the speed with which it gained popularity among British language teaching instructors, gave the movement a national and international acceptance. Thus, this new language teaching method became known as the CLT, and has dominated the EFL/ESL profession since then.⁹ The Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) based on CA, successively, was established in Britain around 1980. Ever since it was established as a language teaching method in ESL and EFL environment, it has received a worldwide popularity among teachers and institutions in different parts of the world. In the following item, different comments from a wide range of scientists and researchers on this literature are cited and interpreted.

To sum up, being able to speak actively is an important communication skill. Active speaking skill will help you and your colleagues more open and useful exchange. Besides that speaking skill is important for career success and also improving personal life.

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